

Teachers' perceptions on the use of learner-centred pedagogies for teaching in basic schools in Hohoe, Ghana

Christopher Yao Dewodo^{1*}, Prem Jotham Heeralal², Daniel Attakumah¹ and Ambrose Agbetorwoka³

¹Department of Education Studies, St. Francis College of Education, Hohoe, Ghana

²Psychology of Education, University of South Africa, South Africa.

³Department of Education Studies, Akatsi College of Education, Akatsi, Ghana

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ABSTRACT

This study presents teachers' perceptions on the use of learner-centred pedagogies in basic schools in Hohoe, Ghana, with emphasis on constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective approaches. Despite policy emphasis on learner-centred instruction, there is limited empirical evidence on how teachers conceptualise and utilise these approaches in Ghanaian classrooms. A descriptive survey design was used to collect data from 364 teachers across 28 schools through complete enumeration. A structured Likert-type questionnaire was used to collect the data, which were analysed using descriptive statistics. The findings indicate that teachers generally hold favourable views of learner-centred pedagogies and are ready to apply them in instructional practice. However, the results also underscore the need for institutional support to ensure sustained implementation. The study provides contextual evidence from Ghana and enriches the broader discourse on learner-centred reforms in sub-Saharan Africa. It recommends strengthened professional development initiatives to enhance pedagogical competence and promote consistent application of learner-centred teaching strategies.

Keywords: Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE), basic schools, learner-centred, pedagogies, perceptions, teachers.

*Corresponding author. Email: dewochris73@gmail.com.

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogy plays a central role in education, serving as the foundation for intellectual growth, problem-solving, and preparing individuals to interact constructively within society. The term is etymologically traced to the Greek *paidagogos*, meaning "leader of children," and historically describes the supervision and discipline involved in raising well-informed individuals (Shah, 2021). In contemporary learning contexts, pedagogy refers to the practices and methods teachers employ to enhance learning (Whiteside et al., 2017). Effective pedagogy requires teachers not only to deliver content but also to nurture their learners' skills, curiosity, and potential.

Researchers emphasise the critical influence of pedagogical approaches on learning outcomes (Curtis, 2019; Hunaepi et al., 2024). Although many advanced nations have achieved improved learning outcomes through innovative teaching practices (Kamal and Kamal, 2015), a substantial body of research in sub-Saharan Africa continues to highlight the pervasive use of ineffective, teacher-centred methods (Adu-Gyamfi, Donkoh and Addo, 2016; Akyeampong, 2017). These approaches, often characterised by rote learning and hierarchical teacher-student relationships, tend to suppress creativity and hinder the development of

learners' problem-solving skills. In response, scholars advocate learner-centred pedagogies that position learners at the heart of the educational process while redefining teachers' roles as facilitators who support and guide learning (Mligo, Mitchell and Bell, 2016).

Learner-centred pedagogy is widely acknowledged for its benefits. It enhances active learner participation, motivation, autonomy, and ownership of learning (Light and Harvey, 2017; Gondwe, 2020). It promotes retention, critical thinking, teamwork, and problem-solving capacities (Blumberg, 2019; Svinicki and McKeachie, 2014). Core strategies within learner-centred pedagogies include constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective approaches (Booth, 2011; Le, Janssen and Wubbels, 2018; Krahenbuhl, 2016). These approaches foster active knowledge construction, teamwork, holistic understanding, and self-assessment, equipping learners with the 21st-century skills necessary for success.

In Ghana, the education system has been significantly influenced by colonial legacies that historically emphasised teacher-centred pedagogical frameworks. This emphasis has led to reliance on rote memorisation and passive teaching methodologies, diminishing learners' capacity to apply knowledge in practical, real-world situations (Ackah-Jnr and Danso, 2019; Biney, 2022). Recent discussions at both international and national levels highlight the imperative to reform these entrenched practices and embrace learner-centred methodologies to align educational systems with contemporary objectives (Kusi, 2020). Teachers' roles are crucial in this transformative process; their beliefs, professional preparation, and instructional practices significantly influence the success of these reforms (Roberts and Clark, 2015). Research has shown that teachers' prior experiences with learner-centred approaches during pre-service training shape their readiness to implement such strategies (Amankwah, 2020). Furthermore, support from school leadership and policymakers remains vital; inadequate institutional backing may undermine reform implementation (Adeyemi, 2020).

Ghana's implementation of a standards-based curriculum in 2019 marked a shift from an objective-based system to one that articulates clear, measurable learning standards expected at each grade level. Unlike the previous approach, which emphasised content coverage and teacher-led transmission, the standards-based model focuses on what learners should know, understand, and be able to do upon completion of instruction. These standards are expressed through performance indicators and core competencies such as critical thinking, creativity,

communication, and problem-solving.

Under this curriculum, teachers are required not merely to deliver content but to facilitate learning experiences that enable students to meet the prescribed standards. Consequently, the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NaCCA) emphasises learner-centred, activity-based, and competency-oriented pedagogy as the cornerstone of successful implementation (Mishiwo, 2022). A key determinant of this success is teachers' competence in selecting and applying instructional methods that align with these standards and promote active participation.

Nonetheless, trends in student performance raise concerns. Results from the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) in the Hohoe Municipality showed a steady increase from 48.38% in 2016 to 63.10% in 2019. However, in 2020, performance declined to 54.00%, representing a 9.10% decrease (Hohoe Municipal Education Service, 2020). This downturn occurred despite the adoption of the learner-centred curriculum, suggesting challenges in its implementation. Although multiple factors influence performance, teachers' instructional methods remain pivotal.

Existing research in other sub-Saharan African contexts, including Ghana, has primarily focused on the effects of learner-centred methods on pupil outcomes (Angbing et al., 2014; Asimeng-Boahene and Baffoe, 2013). Only a limited body of work has examined teachers' attitudes toward these approaches, even though teachers play a central role in curriculum implementation. Teachers' beliefs, perceptions, and experiences significantly shape instructional practices and determine the success of new pedagogical approaches. If teachers experience loss of confidence, difficulties, or develop negative attitudes toward learner-centred methods, reforms may fail to achieve their intended outcomes.

The existing gap in the literature highlights the need to examine how teachers in Ghana conceptualise and practise learner-centred pedagogies. Understanding teachers' perspectives is critical for two reasons. First, it clarifies the challenges and opportunities that shape curriculum implementation. Second, it ensures that policy reforms are informed by classroom realities, making them more contextually grounded and sustainable.

This study analyses teachers' perceptions of learner-centred pedagogies in basic schools in the Hohoe Municipality. It aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on effective pedagogical practices while offering implications for implementing the standards-based curriculum in Ghana.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Figure 1.

As shown in Figure 1, the current study employs a multilevel conceptual framework that integrates Social Constructivism and Cultural-Historical Activity Theory (CHAT) to promote learner-centred pedagogies within the broader teaching system. Perceptions and teacher intentions are interpreted in terms of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and reinforced by the construct of self-efficacy. The implementation of constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective methods is also informed by Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle and Schön's reflective practice framework. These positions, in conjunction, illuminate the psychological and environmental variables that are determinative in the adoption of learner-centred pedagogies among basic school teachers.

Recent shifts in global educational discourse underscore a strong movement toward learner-centred pedagogy, where instructional processes prioritise active engagement, cognitive autonomy, and the co-construction of knowledge. Within this paradigm, teaching is understood not merely as the transmission of content but as the facilitation of meaningful learning experiences that allow learners to interpret, apply, and reflect on new knowledge. Le, Janssen and Wubbels (2018) identify five dominant pedagogical models that currently guide learner-centred practice: constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective pedagogies. These approaches collectively advance deeper learning by encouraging students to articulate ideas, negotiate meaning, draw connections across concepts, and evaluate their own thinking. Constructivist pedagogy foregrounds learner agency and experiential meaning-making; collaborative learning emphasises shared problem-solving and social interaction; inquiry-based approaches position

learners as investigators who generate and test ideas; integrative pedagogy connects disciplinary knowledge to real-world contexts; and reflective pedagogy cultivates metacognition as a core component of instructional practice. Together, these frameworks offer a robust theoretical lens for analysing teachers' pedagogical perceptions and practices. Accordingly, they constitute the conceptual foundations of the present study and guide its interpretation of learner-centred instructional dynamics.

Constructivism represents a significant epistemological shift from transmissive models of teaching toward approaches that emphasise active knowledge construction. Grounded in the works of Piaget and Vygotsky, constructivism positions learners as agents who interpret, negotiate, and transform experiences into meaningful understanding (Bhattacharjee, 2015). Contemporary literature demonstrates its influence on curriculum reform, science learning, and pedagogical innovation, particularly through its emphasis on inquiry, scaffolding, and learner autonomy (Emery et al., 2020). As a result, many national curricula integrate constructivist principles to promote higher-order thinking and deeper engagement (Ampadu and Danso, 2018).

Despite its prominence, teachers' attitudes toward constructivist pedagogy remain mixed. Evidence from Pakistan (Wali et al., 2021) and Turkey (Ozturk-Akar, 2019) suggests generally favourable dispositions, with teachers highlighting its potential to enhance creativity, motivation, and learner participation. However, concerns persist. Some educators conflate constructivism with diminished structure, leading to apprehension about classroom control, assessment, and the predictability of learning outcomes (Anderson and Stillman, 2013; LePage-Kljajic, 2019). Gatete (2025) notes that although

constructivist practices enjoy broad theoretical support, debates continue regarding their feasibility in resource-constrained or examination-driven systems.

Collaborative learning extends constructivist assumptions by positioning knowledge construction within social dialogue and collective problem-solving. Typically implemented through structured group tasks, it encourages negotiation, shared responsibility, and co-construction of meaning (Osipov, 2017). Teachers frequently endorse collaborative learning for its contribution to engagement, communication abilities, teamwork, and problem-solving (Silva, Lopes, Dominguez and Morais, 2022). Nevertheless, implementation challenges are well documented. Difficulties with managing group dynamics, ensuring equitable participation, and assessing individual contributions often undermine its effectiveness (Larson and Murphy, 2023). Subject-specific expectations also shape teacher perceptions; for instance, while some mathematics teachers value collaboration for enhancing reasoning skills, others express concerns about reduced individual accountability (Capar and Tarim, 2015). These tensions highlight the need for carefully designed structures that balance collective and individual learning goals.

Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), grounded in Dewey's philosophy of experiential education, frames learners as investigators who generate questions, test ideas, and construct knowledge through exploration (Caswell and LaBrie, 2017; Trna, Trnova and Siboe, 2012). Teachers generally view IBL as stimulating curiosity, critical thinking, and conceptual understanding (Pedrosa-de-Jesus, Guerra and Watts, 2017; Agbo et al., 2021). However, its successful implementation requires substantial pedagogical content knowledge, facilitation skills, and instructional time. Barriers such as rigid curricular pacing, high-stakes testing, and difficulties maintaining classroom order frequently constrain teachers' use of IBL (Fichten, 2019). Scholars emphasise the need for sustained professional development, access to instructional resources, and supportive school cultures to enhance teachers' confidence and competence in implementing inquiry methods (Kpeglo, 2024).

Integrated pedagogy promotes holistic learning by connecting concepts across discipline boundaries, thereby fostering knowledge transfer, real-world application, and broader cognitive development (Herodotou et al., 2019). Teachers often appreciate its capacity to enhance students' critical thinking, engagement, and authentic problem-solving (Okolie et al., 2022; Amerstorfer et al., 2021). Integration also aligns with twenty-first-century curriculum reforms that emphasise interdisciplinarity and relevance to learners' lived experiences (Helle et al., 2006; Van Es et al., 2017). However, challenges remain. Designing cohesive interdisciplinary curricula is complex (Kim, 2018), and teachers frequently express concern about superficial coverage of specialised content, particularly in mathematics and science (Barnett et al.,

2018). Additionally, questions regarding role delineation, assessment complexity, and instructional leadership complicate sustained implementation (Sarkar et al., 2020; Kim, 2018).

Reflective pedagogy foregrounds critical self-examination of teaching and learning processes, enabling practitioners to analyse their assumptions, refine instructional decisions, and foster meaningful professional growth (Martinez-Maldonado et al., 2019). Research demonstrates that reflective practice enhances teachers' autonomy, creativity, and adaptive expertise, while also supporting learners' metacognition and a deeper understanding (Farrell, 2015; Barton and Ryan, 2020). Professional learning communities further strengthen reflection by providing social spaces for dialogue, shared inquiry, and collective problem-solving (Playsted, 2019). However, reflective practice is not universally embraced. Some teachers perceive it as time-intensive, abstract, or incompatible with heavy workloads (Makransky and Petersen, 2019). Others mistrust reflective documentation due to fear of scrutiny, accountability pressures, or misalignment with context-specific classroom realities (Yu, 2018; Nguyen, Foster and Kim, 2020). The privileging of quantitative indicators, such as test scores, over qualitative evidence also reduces the institutional value placed on reflective pedagogy (Schön, 2017; Kaufman, 2018).

Across these five pedagogical approaches, constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrated, and reflective pedagogies, a shared commitment to learner-centredness is evident. However, each approach foregrounds a distinct dimension of learning: personal meaning-making, social interaction, exploration, interdisciplinarity, and metacognition, respectively. While teachers' perceptions are generally favourable, persistent concerns about classroom management, assessment, workload, and systemic support continue to shape their willingness and ability to adopt learner-centred methods. Moreover, existing research is often fragmented by country, subject area, or localised case studies, with limited comparative evidence across pedagogical approaches.

Consequently, further research is needed to explore how teachers conceptualise, adapt, and enact these pedagogies within their specific school contexts. Such insights are essential for understanding the practical realities of learner-centred education and informing policy reforms aimed at improving instructional quality and learner outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed a descriptive survey design to explore teachers' perceptions on the use of learner-centred pedagogies in basic schools in Hohoe. This design was deemed appropriate because the study aimed to

gather single-point data from various respondents to uncover teachers' views on learner-centred pedagogies without any manipulation (Amedahe and Asamoah-Gyimah, 2015). The study targeted all basic school teachers in public schools within the Hohoe Township. According to records from the Statistics Unit of the Hohoe Municipal Education Directorate (2022), there are 364 basic school teachers in 28 basic schools within the Hohoe Township. To enhance the study's external validity, the census method was used to involve all 364 teachers.

Data were collected using a self-developed, five-point Likert-type scale questionnaire (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree) to explore teachers' perceptions of learner-centred pedagogies. Ethical clearance was obtained and attached to a research permission letter sent to the Hohoe Municipal Director of Education for approval. Following approval, the researcher visited the schools, presented the permission letter to the headteachers, and sought their consent before commencing data collection.

The study employed a single, structured questionnaire developed from key data items identified in relevant empirical literature and national policy documents on learner-centred pedagogy. Instrument development followed a deductive approach, in which theoretical constructs and policy directives were translated into measurable indicators. The final questionnaire comprised 18 items organised into two main sections.

Section A contained three items capturing respondents' demographic characteristics, including gender, highest educational qualification, and years of teaching experience.

Section B consisted of 15 Likert-scale statements derived directly from the theoretical and policy-based data items that guided questionnaire construction. These items were organised into five core dimensions of learner-centred pedagogy:

1. Teachers' perceptions of constructivist pedagogy
2. Teachers' perceptions of collaborative pedagogy
3. Teachers' perceptions of inquiry-based pedagogy
4. Teachers' perceptions of integrative pedagogy
5. Teachers' perceptions of reflective pedagogy

These dimensions represent dominant learner-centred approaches emphasised in contemporary pedagogical literature and Ghana's standards-based curriculum reform frameworks.

Regarding data collection, the researcher scheduled specific dates with participating schools to meet teachers and administer the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to all 364 teachers across 28 basic schools in Hohoe. Participants completed the questionnaire at their convenience and returned it the following day.

Prior to data collection, issues of confidentiality, anonymity, and informed consent were thoroughly addressed, and teachers were assured that participation

was voluntary and responses would be used solely for research purposes.

The researcher designated five weeks for data collection, which took place from 15th May to 20th June 2024. Prior to fieldwork, formal permission was obtained from the Hohoe Municipal Education Directorate and from the headteachers of all participating basic schools. During the first week (15th–22nd May 2024), the researcher scheduled visits to the 28 schools, introduced the study to staff, and arranged suitable dates for questionnaire administration.

During weeks two to four (23rd May–14th June 2024), the researcher visited each school according to the agreed schedule, met participating teachers during their free periods or after instructional hours, and administered the structured questionnaire. Respondents were given 24 hours to complete the instrument at their convenience and returned the completed questionnaires the following day. Matters of informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation were emphasised prior to the distribution of the questionnaires.

The final week (15th–20th June 2024) was used for follow-ups, retrieving outstanding questionnaires, verifying returned responses, and documenting the overall response rate. In total, questionnaires were administered to 364 teachers across the 28 participating schools.

Before data collection began, the questionnaire was pilot-tested to ensure its adequacy in six basic schools: Ho Kpodzi Basic School, Philip Akpo R/C Girls, Kabore School Complex, Ho Bankoe E.P., Ho RIIS Presbyterian School Complex, and Ho Methodist Basic School, all located in the Ho Township in the Volta Region of Ghana. This pilot test aimed to evaluate the internal consistency of the items. Piloting the instrument helped identify and rectify ambiguous and unclear items on the scales before the data collection. The questionnaire's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a value of 0.81. This indicates that the instrument had minimal errors and demonstrated high internal consistency (Ikart, 2019). The researcher employed a structured data-analytic procedure, using descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations.

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics of teachers

This section presents results on the teachers based on demographic distribution. The demographic information included gender, teaching experience and educational qualification of teachers. Table 1 presents details of the demographic distribution.

An inspection of Table 1 shows that out of a sample of 364, 163 of them were males (44.8%), whereas 201 of them were females (55.2%). This suggests that the responses were dominated by female teachers. This is

obvious, as the population of teachers in Basic Schools in Ghana is often dominated by females. Regarding the educational qualifications of the respondents, the majority, 242 (66.5%), held a first degree as their highest level of education. Following this, 75 (20.6%) had attained a diploma as their highest level of education, 36 (9.9%) held a master's degree as their highest level of education, and

11 (3%) had completed a certificate programme as their highest level of education. In furtherance, the majority of the respondents 159 (43.7%) had taught for a period of 11–15 years; 88 (24.2%) of the respondents had taught for a period of 6–10 years; 84 (23.1%) had taught for 16 years and beyond; and 33 (9%) of the respondents had taught for less than 5 years in the basic school.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of teachers (N =364).

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	163	44.8
Female	201	55.2
Educational qualification		
Certificate	11	3.0
Diploma	75	20.6
First Degree	242	66.5
Masters	36	9.9
Years of teaching experience		
Less than 5 years	33	9.0
6-10 years	88	24.2
11-15 years	159	43.7
16 years and above	84	23.1

Source: Field Survey (2023).

Figures 2, 3 and 4 present a graphical representation of the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Details of these graphs are presented in the subsequent paragraphs.

Figure 2. Gender of teachers.

Figure 3. Educational qualification.

■ Less than 5 years ■ 6-10 years ■ 11-15 years ■ 16 years and above

Figure 4. Years of teaching experience.

Teachers' perceptions regarding the use of learner-centred pedagogical approaches were sought. As shown in Table 2, a greater proportion of the respondents generally agreed to the fact that they had some perceptions about constructivism's pedagogical approach ($M = 3.88$, $SD = .84$). Specifically, most of the respondents reported that the constructivism approach makes students responsible for their own learning ($M = 4.07$, $SD = .94$). The respondents also agreed to the fact that the constructivism approach is very effective for instructional delivery compared to the lecture method" ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 1.23$). The respondents further agreed to the fact that failure to use constructivism as an instructional approach could result in poor academic performance on the part of the students ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.28$).

Regarding the issue of collaborative pedagogical approach, most of the respondents generally agreed that they had some perceptions about this teaching approach

($M = 3.77$, $SD = .66$). Topmost among respondents' views are: the collaborative approach helps learners to understand and retain what they have learned ($M = 4.06$, $SD = .75$), the approach helps students to work in groups, and this improves their learning ($M = 3.81$, $SD = 1.02$), and it is difficult to maintain class control when using this approach ($M = 3.43$, $SD = 1.12$).

Concerning the issue of inquiry pedagogical approach, the majority of the respondents generally agreed to the fact that they had some perceptions about this teaching method ($M = 3.05$, $SD = .71$). The respondents specifically reported that learners develop problem-solving skills through the use of the inquiry technique ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 1.05$), and the approach helps learners draw appropriate conclusions from observations ($M = 3.24$, $SD = 1.32$). Respondents, however, disagreed with the fact that the inquiry pedagogical approach is unable to guide learners in obtaining first-hand information ($M = 1.88$, $SD = 1.11$).

Table 2. Teachers' perceptions of learner-centred pedagogical approaches.

Approaches	Mean	SD
Constructivism approach		
Constructivism approach is very effective compared to the lecture method.	3.9121	1.22327
Failure to use a constructivism approach to teach can result in low academic performance.	3.6703	1.27536
Constructivism approach makes students responsible for their own learning.	4.0714	.94204
Mean of means	3.8846	.84349
Collaborative approach		
Working in groups improves children's learning.	3.8077	1.02118
The approach helps learners to understand and retain what they have learnt.	4.0632	.74882
It is difficult to maintain class control when using this approach.	3.4286	1.12466
Mean of means	3.7665	0.66029
Inquiry approach		
The approach is unable to guide learners to obtain first-hand information.	1.8764	1.11765
Learners develop problem-solving skills through the use of the inquiry technique.	4.0357	1.05043
The approach helps learners to draw appropriate conclusions from their observations.	3.2445	1.32702
Mean of means	3.0522	0.71112
Integrative approach		
Integrative approach facilitates the transfer of knowledge from one field of study to another.	4.2198	.88827
New learning is applied to practical life situations when an integrative approach is used.	3.8462	.93800
The approach develops the creativity and critical thinking abilities of learners.	3.5192	1.11447
Mean of means	3.86173	0.67903
Reflective approach		
Reflective approach guides teachers to select the right strategies at any stage of lesson delivery.	4.3462	.67702
Learners are able to retain knowledge with the continuous use of a reflective approach by teachers during lesson delivery.	4.1236	.95554
The approach encourages active interaction in class between the teacher and learners.	4.2830	.85257
Mean of means	4.2509	0.63606

Source: Field Survey (2023).

Regarding the issue of the integrative approach, a greater proportion of the respondents generally agreed to the fact that they had some perceptions about the integrative pedagogical approach ($M = 3.8$, $SD = .68$). Topmost among these perceptions are that the integrative approach facilitates the transfer of knowledge from one field of study to another ($M = 4.22$, $SD = .89$), new learning is applied to practical life situations when the integrative approach is used ($M = 3.85$, $SD = .94$), the approach develops the creativity and critical thinking abilities of learners ($M = 3.52$, $SD = 1.11$).

Concerning the issue of reflective pedagogical approach, most of the respondents generally agreed to the fact that they had some perceptions about this approach ($M = 4.25$, $SD = .64$). Specifically, the majority of the respondents agreed to the following assertions: the reflective approach guides teachers to select the right strategies at any stage of lesson delivery ($M = 4.35$, SD

$= .68$), the approach encourages active interaction in class between the teacher and learners ($M = 4.28$, $SD = .85$), and learners are able to retain knowledge with the continuous use of this approach by the instructor ($M = 4.12$, $SD = .96$).

The findings of the study revealed that, generally, basic school teachers within the Hohoe Township had positive perceptions regarding the use of learner-centred pedagogical approaches in their teaching profession. Generally, it was discovered that learner-centred pedagogical approaches such as constructivism, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective were held in high esteem by basic school teachers within the Hohoe Township. Thus, teachers generally expressed positive perceptions regarding the aforementioned learner-centred pedagogical approaches, which are often used in teaching basic school students.

Regarding the issue of teachers' perceptions on the use of learner-centred pedagogical approaches, a graphical

representation is provided in Figure 4 to show the trend of teachers' perceptions on the use of the various learner-

centred pedagogical approaches. Details of this trend are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Learner-centred pedagogical approaches.

The findings of this study showed that, in general, basic school teachers in Hohoe Township had favourable attitudes towards the application of learner-centred teaching methods. Specifically, the five methods under study — constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective — were all found to be effective in teaching in elementary schools. The teachers expressed that the methods improve the learners' responsibility, instill participation, and enhance learning achievements.

DISCUSSION

Constructivist pedagogy

Teachers in Hohoe viewed constructivist teaching as empowering learners to take ownership of their own learning. This perception aligns with Wali et al. (2021) and Ozturk-Akar (2019), who also found that teachers value constructivist approaches for stimulating creativity, motivation, and attention. These upbeat perceptions mark the acknowledgement of teachers' awareness of constructivism underpinning deeper learning. By contrast with Anderson and Stillman (2013) and LePage-Kijajic (2019), however, where the authors observed that several teachers regarded constructivism as unmanageable and ineffectual with worries that classroom control is lost, the discrepancy implies that context is a key factor in forming the receptiveness of teachers to constructivist approaches with the implication that the teachers in Hohoe seemed more willing to give up control in favour of autonomy for

learners.

Collaborative pedagogy

Likewise, Hohoe teachers reported positive opinions of collaborative pedagogy, highlighting that it improves engagement, retention, and critical thinking. These results align with the study by Silva et al. (2022), which found that collaboration is a method through which students can exchange different views and improve teamwork, a valuable skill in the real world. However, contrary evidence from Larson and Murphy (2023) and Capar and Tarim (2015) suggests that teachers are concerned with issues such as group behaviour, unequal participation, and decreased personal responsibility. Although the concerns are genuine, the positive attitudes reflected in the report from Hohoe suggest that the teachers in the region may have effective methods for tackling the issues.

Inquiry-based pedagogy

Teachers in this study also identified inquiry teaching as key in encouraging problem-solving and higher-level thought. The finding is in agreement with Pedrosa-de-Jesus et al. (2017), Fichten (2019), and Agbo et al. (2021), whose studies also identified that teachers recognised the ability of inquiry in cultivating creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Such similarity in findings across studies demonstrates the efficacy of inquiry approaches in providing students with the required 21st-century

competencies.

Integrative pedagogy

Teachers' attitudes toward integrative pedagogy were similarly favourable, with many highlighting the approach's ability to transfer knowledge between disciplines. These attitudes are reinforced by Helle et al. (2006), Van Es et al. (2017), and Corradi et al. (2021), whose work likewise cited integrative methods as drivers of interdisciplinary knowledge. Moreover, Okolie et al. (2022) and Amerstorfer et al. (2021) confirm that integrative pedagogy renders learning more relevant and meaningful by grounding concepts in real-world applications. While challenges identified by Kim (2018) and Barnett et al. (2018), such as the lack of curriculum correspondence and the danger of superficiality, remain considerations of considerable importance, the favourable attitude of the Hohoe teachers suggests a willingness to work through them in favour of encouraging Holistic learning.

Reflective pedagogy

Finally, teachers expressed positive views of reflective pedagogy, recognising the value it has in informing instructional decision-making and development of practice. These outcomes align with those of Barton and Ryan (2020) and Farrell (2015), which emphasise the role of reflection in facilitating professional growth, self-awareness, and adaptability in teaching. In sharp contrast, other researchers, such as Yu (2018), expressed negative views, suggesting that reflection is oppressive or exposes teachers to professional risk. This discrepancy highlights the importance of institutional facilitation in ensuring that reflection becomes a valuable learning experience rather than a controversial one.

Generally, the findings reveal that the teachers in Hohoe are receptive to learner-centred teaching and are aware of the role of teacher behaviour in encouraging student participation, problem-solving, and interdisciplinary applications. The positive attitudes manifest suggest a disposition towards a move from teacher-centred to learner-centred teaching approaches. However, the conflicting evidence from the literature reminds us of the need for ongoing professional development and structural support to overcome concerns regarding classroom management, responsibility in collaborative learning, and integrated curricula.

Conclusion

This study examined teachers' perceptions of learner-centred pedagogical approaches in basic schools in Hohoe, Ghana, with a focus on constructivist,

collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective pedagogies. The findings revealed that teachers generally hold positive perceptions of these approaches, acknowledging their value in promoting learner autonomy, enhancing problem-solving and critical thinking skills, facilitating knowledge transfer, and supporting reflective practice.

Notably, the favourable teacher attitude in Hohoe stands in sharp contrast to the results in certain foreign studies that report concerns regarding classroom management, teacher accountability, and curriculum relevance. These results imply that situational variables, such as cultural demand, professional development opportunities, and site-level teaching emphases, significantly influence teachers' views of learner-centred teaching methods.

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